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Introducing Professional Ethics as a Soft Skill **An example in the Civil Engineering bachelor's degree program in UPV.**

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ABSTRACT

According to the Civil Engineering bachelor's degree program in Spain, students should have acquired, among others, the skill "to understand and assume the ethical and professional responsibility of the activity of the Civil Engineer". This knowledge is taught in an optative subject called "Ethics of civil engineering", and also through the transversal or soft skill "ethical, environmental and professional responsibility" that is covered in several subjects of the program. Since not all the students enrol the specific subject, learning professional ethics through the soft skills becomes of special importance.

This communication presents the methodology used in the subject "Constructions Materials" from the second year to introduce this soft skill. The approach consists on having this skill present in all the sessions in the classroom, and to obtain evidences of the steps learned by the student, a rubric is proposed, which allows the teacher to evaluate the acquisition of the competence in an agile and truthful way.

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Current situation shows that, more often than expected, civil engineering students and professionals have difficulties in identifying malpractices in the development of their profession, probably due to their high frequency. To overcome this situation, students need to be fully aware of the consequences of their decisions and the severity of their mistakes. Society needs engineers able to understand the full scope of their work, including the ethical responsibility derived from their position. Engineering Schools must dedicate strong commitment to improve the integral formation of their graduates with special emphasis on professional ethics.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 The beginning of the introduction of soft skills in the curriculum.

The arrival of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) forced the redesign of Spanish university degrees to adapt to a common reference framework to make qualifications for the different EHEA countries more understandable across different systems [1]. In 2001, the Spanish Government published the Organic Law 6/2001 indicating the compromise of convergence to the EHEA [2]. From 2003, the Ministry of Education and Science published reports that talked on the objective of "providing a university education that harmoniously integrates the basic generic skills, skills related to the integral formation of persons and more specific skills that enable a professional orientation that allows graduates integration in the labour market".

Having these frameworks as a basis, the Civil Engineering Schools of Spain began to design the new degree programs incorporating the transversal or soft skills that the students had to acquire. However, even though they were assigned to different subjects, during the first years of implementation of these new degrees' programs, transversal skills were not systematically implemented and evaluated, which means that their acquisition was not strictly guaranteed.

For this reason, an initiative of the Vice-Rectorate for Studies, Quality and Accreditation of the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), supported by the strategic plan UPV 2015-2020, developed the institutional project of incorporating transversal skills in the curriculum of graduates of the UPV [3]. The fundamental objective of this action is that the students acquire and accredit the achievement of these transversal skills. Based on guidelines and national and international standards, specialized publications and taking into account the regulations or recommendations of some degree programs, the UPV defined 13 transversal competences that should be trained in all curricula (*Table 1*). Most of these skills were already being trained on a regular basis, but in most cases were not evaluated.

Table 1. Transversal skills in all degrees of the UPV.

Code	Transversal Skill
CT-01	Comprehension and integration
CT-02	Application and practical thinking
CT-03	Analysis and resolution of problems
CT-04	Innovation, creativity and entrepreneurship
CT-05	Design and project
CT-06	Teamwork and leadership
CT-07	Ethical, environmental and professional responsibility
CT-08	Effective Communication
CT-09	Critical thinking
CT-10	Knowledge of contemporary problems
CT-11	Life-long learning
CT-12	Planning and time management
CT-13	Specific instruments

To evaluate the acquisition of these soft skills, in 2015 the UPV Institute of Education Sciences (ICE), in collaboration with professors of different degrees, developed several rubrics which had to be achieved in different courses differentiating levels of skill domain: first level domain for the first and second courses of bachelor's degree, second level domain for the third and fourth courses and, third level of domain for the master's degree.

As a result of this project, the Civil Engineering School of UPV redefined the soft skills that should be included in the degree program and the assessment criteria for the achievement of the skill using the rubrics. To do this, regardless of the number of subjects that train these skills, several subjects were established as a checkpoint to evaluate the acquisition of the soft skills in different courses of the bachelor's degree program covering the different levels of domain. In this framework, the subject "Construction Materials" from the second year of the degree of Civil Engineering became a checkpoint of the soft skill seven (CT-07) "Ethical, environmental and professional responsibility" for the first level of domain.

1.2 The role of accreditations

At the same time as the introduction of soft skills, the Civil Engineering, B.Eng. and M.Eng programs from the Civil Engineering School of Valencia obtained the ABET accreditation on October 1st, 2015. During the current school year, they have been renovated and will remain active until the September 30th, 2024. ABET accreditation ensures that a university program meets the quality standards of the profession for which that program prepares graduates. Thus, it may help students to choose programs with quality guarantees and employers to select well-prepared graduates to exercise the profession. As a matter of fact, in Spain only two bachelor's degree programs in Civil Engineering have the ABET accreditation.

The quality criteria for accrediting bachelor level engineering programs considers eight specific criteria: 1) the students (admission, progress, evaluation...), 2) the

establishment of educational objectives that the graduates will reach a few years after their graduation, 3) the competences that the students acquire throughout their studies, 4) the process of continuous improvement, 5) the curriculum, 6) the teaching staff, 7) the facilities and infrastructures available, and 8) the institutional support that guarantees the teaching of the degree.

To obtain the accreditation, the bachelor's degree program must have documented student outcomes that support the program educational objectives [4]. Among these outcomes, one covers the "ability to design a system, component, or process to meet desired needs within realistic constraints such as economic, environmental, social, political, ethical, health and safety, manufacturability, and sustainability", and other directly refers to the "understanding of professional and ethical responsibility". These two points are directly related to the soft skill "ethical, environmental and professional responsibility". Therefore, it is not only essential to train the learning outcome, it is also necessary to obtain evidences of the outcomes to achieve the accreditation.

For this reason, it is necessary to design an activity that permits a quick and efficient evaluation of the acquisition of this competence/skill and obtaining an evidence to certify it.

2 DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ACTIVITY

2.1 First implementation attempts

As a result of the concern for the introduction of soft skills in the student's curriculum, a project of innovation and educational improvement (PIME) was elaborated. The PIME title was "The introduction of professional responsibility in the curriculum of Civil Engineering degree" and it was developed during the course 2013-14. This project involved different subjects from different courses of the degree program, and it was previous to the strategic plan UPV2015-2020 mentioned above. From that moment, two classroom actions were carried out and their outcomes were collected as a result of the PIME project.

The first action aimed to raise students' awareness of the professional responsibility that they will assume when graduating, throughout the development of the subjects that were involved in the project. This action is based on the experiences described in the classroom by professors, who describe real experiences and decisions taken in the professional field. These experiences undoubtedly influence the training of students and transmit the responsibility that goes hand in hand with their professional work. This is the most usual way for Spanish undergraduates to become aware of the responsibility of their profession.

The second action involved the organization of two practical sessions throughout the course. In these sessions, moral dilemmas [5] were raised and the students had to discuss in small groups and then, to discuss in the whole class in a general debate. Students work and knowledge of this skill was evaluated through a rubric specifically designed for this activity. Several obstacles appeared during these sessions. One of the main difficulties was that many students were facing a moral dilemma for the first

time and thus, they did not know the strategies and tools to solve them nor could they consider all the factors affecting the dilemma. Another difficulty was that the focus was made in the dilemmas directly related with the subjects in which they were taught, and they were not designed to have a progressively developing nature, which produced that in some cases younger students had to solve dilemmas of high complexity. In addition, several professors expressed their concerns over their ability to perform this type of training. To work appropriately the moral dilemmas, the professor must know and understand codes of ethics, and justify the final solution following the thinking process of moral reasoning to determine whether an idea is right or wrong. Finally, another problem detected with this methodology was the soft skill “ethical, environmental and professional responsibility” was only trained during the two sessions in which the moral dilemmas were raised, and it was not present in the rest of the sessions of the course.

Despite all the problems identified, the experience was considered as very positive since it allowed to clarify the students’ knowledge of this soft skill, as well as the a better understanding of the limitations of the professors and, thanks to this activity, a first rubric was designed to evaluate the acquisition of this soft skill.

After the publication in 2015, of several rubrics by ICE, for the different skills and differentiating levels of skill domain, we realized that the difficulty level was too high for second course students (first level domain). Using as basis all the work developed in our previous attempts and the new information provided by ICE, we designed a new activity to implement the acquisition of this soft skill in all classroom sessions using a suitable level of difficulty.

2.2 Activity development and evaluation

With the knowledge acquired in the previous experiences, and with the strong conviction that “ethical, environmental and professional responsibility” is a fundamental skill for our students to achieve professional excellence, we re-designed an activity to work and evaluate this soft skill during all classroom sessions.

The activity was planned considering that it was going to be carried out during the second course of the degree and thus, it corresponded with the first level of domain of this skill. In order to facilitate the evaluation of the activity, the rubric designed by the ICE working group was used, whose purpose is to test whether the student has reached the level required for this skill, defined as: “the student will be able to question reality and be aware of the concepts and values from which it is built”. This rubric is shown in *Fig. 1*, and each indicator is evaluated using the scores from A (highest score) to D (lowest score).

INDICATORS	DESCRIPTORS			
	D-Unreached	C-Under Development	B-Good	A-Excellent
Become aware of another way of seeing and perceiving things	They have difficulty understanding that there is a plurality of ideas and people that consider and value reality in a different way	Accepts without question the judgments of other people	Explicitly and reasonably assumes the differences	Incorporate ideas from others into your own reasoning and judgment
Accept critically new perspectives	It only takes into account the perspective of those who are most involved in the course of an action and eludes the point of view of third parties	They maintain critically what has to be preserved in a dialogical positioning In a reasonable positioning	They capture and show sensitivity to the needs and interests of others, their Feelings, values, opinions and reasons	They dialogue constructively with the aim of contributing to the understanding and the solution of problems, respecting and recognizing the pretensions of validity of the other pinions
Difference facts and opinions or interpretations in the arguments of others	They do not differentiate opinions or subjective facts judgments	They question judgments or decisions based on opinions, assessments, etc.	They can difference, objective facts of opinions and evaluations	They can analyze justifiably judgments or decisions based on opinions, evaluations, etc.
Reflect on the consequences and effects that decisions and proposals have on open	There is no evidence that they are aware of the effects of the proposed decisions	They provide for the practical implications of decisions and proposals	They analyze advantages or disadvantages of the effects of the proposed decisions.	Provides ideas for improvement
Recognized the ethical and deontological concepts of the profession	Thinks that ethics belongs to the personal sphere	Expresses basic moral opinions	Expresses moral opinions about the correctness or incorrectness of an activity or action	It is able to elaborate arguments where principles and moral judgments come into play Linked to the profession

Fig. 1. Rubric UPV-CT-07. Ethical, environmental and professional responsibility.

For the activity, the students prepare a presentation to expose in the classroom news published in the press or any media, where they detected an inappropriate behaviour conducted by individuals or companies. These inappropriate behaviours may be, among others, cases of corruption, poor professional practices, poor use of resources, cause of ecological damage, etc. The main theme of the news should cover preferably (but not limited to) civil engineering problems.

This presentation can be performed either individually or in small groups, with a maximum length of five minutes. The presentation of the students should explain the facts and discuss at least the following aspects:

- Agents involved in the case
- Identification of the inappropriate action(s)
- Identification of the motivation to perform that inappropriate action(s) (economic enrichment, professional promotion, fear of reprisals, etc.)

The presentation is followed by a discussion/debate involving all the students. The professor evaluates the students using as information what happened in the classroom during the presentation and discussion stages, and using the rubric shown in *Fig. 1* as support for this evaluation. In the specific case of group work, all members of the group will obtain the same grade for the presentation but depending on their degree of participation during the debate, this grade may vary. *Fig. 2* shows some of the works presented by the students.

Fig. 2. Examples of the works presented by the students

3 ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

The activity presented has been carried out since 2015 in the subject “Construction Materials” and the results can be considered highly satisfactory. This type of activity presents several advantages over previous activities, including:

- The soft skill trained is present in all classroom sessions, which guarantees its presence throughout the course.
- When making presentations and oral discussion, the professor, who is present in the classroom, is able to evaluate in a fast, agile and direct way with the help of the rubric. This avoids lengthy corrective writing assignment.
- The evidences of the evaluation are the news, presented by the students in any format (.pdf, .ppt, etc.).
- The students are active during the debate incorporating diverse points of view and enriching the activity.
- The debate should be used by the professor to ensure the acquisition of the expected learning outcome.

This work explains the results obtained for this activity for three courses 2015-16 to 2017-18. So far, all the students who attend the courses during the presentations of the works obtain a positive assessment in the acquisition of the expected skill level (A or B scores). Fig. 3 shows the detailed results obtained after the evaluation of this soft skill, differentiating the score (left graph) and combining the results depending on the type of assessment (right graph), either positive (A, B) or negative (C, D).

Fig. 3. Percentage of students with each score in the last three academic years.

As can be seen in *Fig. 3*, most students obtained A or B scores, and none of the students obtained D scores. However, there is still a percentage around 25% of the students who obtained C scores, which means that they did not clearly identify unethical behaviours. During the year 2017-18, there was a percentage of students that did not attend and thus, were not evaluated. Frequently, the students who obtained a C score misinterpreted the occurrence of accidents, which are facts that are impossible to anticipate, without the implication of unethical behaviour. This indicates that students should be made aware that even though many accidents can be prevented with adequate safety conditions at work, the occurrence of an accident is not necessarily caused by a lack of professional ethics.

The importance of achieving this skill related with professional ethics is highlighted in the White Books published for the Spanish Civil Engineering degrees [4], when enumerating the skills and competences that a Civil Engineer should possess. One of these skills is “to be prepared to practise the profession, having clear consciousness of its human, economic, social, legal and ethical dimensions”. In spite of that, the knowledge covered in this category is considered by this document as complementary, far from civil engineering basic subjects.

The authors consider that all students who complete their studies and aim to obtain a degree in civil engineering, should have been evaluated with a positive assessment of this soft skill, which is translated in A or B scores. With an appropriated inclusion and training of this soft skill during the whole degree program, all students should be able to obtain its competences by the end of the program. Our society cannot admit professionals who are not capable of detecting unethical behaviour.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work has presented an activity to work and evaluate the soft skill "Ethical, environmental and professional responsibility" valid for the level of domain required for a second-year course. The activity is based on the students presenting and discussing news that show unethical behaviour. This activity allowed us to introduce the skill during the course, to directly collect the learning evidences and, to quickly evaluate the acquisition of the skill using a rubric. The experience of this activity is considered by the authors as very positive for the introduction of the soft skill.

Several degrees from UPV include specific subjects related to professional ethics. Undoubtedly, it is a question of significant importance that the students should train at different stages during the higher education programs.

In the opinion of the authors, the most appropriated approach to include professional ethics is to have specific subjects related to ethics, environmental and professional responsibility in the curriculum and, in parallel, to strengthen the skill throughout the curriculum using transversal contents. This approach would guarantee that certain skills are acquired during university studies. In fact, as stated by Prof. Cortina [6] “a society demonstrates that a subject seems essential for the formation of a professional when it explicitly includes it in its curriculum”.

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